

PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF GOVERNING COUNCILS' ROLES ON THE MANAGEMENT OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study was conducted on perceived influence of Governing Councils' roles on the management of tertiary institutions of Jigawa state, Nigeria. The study hinged on survey research design, and the instrument used was adapted questionnaire named as "Governing Council and Management of Tertiary Institutions Questionnaire" (GCAMTIQ) that was administered to 302 selected sample. Research questions and hypotheses were formulated and answered; the result of the findings revealed that Governing Councils have positive influence on the appointment of Principal Officers, provision of infrastructural facilities, funding, and staff recruitment, development and discipline in the area of the study. The study therefore, concluded that Governing Councils are playing significant roles in the management of tertiary institutions of Jigawa state, Nigeria. The study recommended among other things that Governing Councils of tertiary institutions should continue maintaining the tempo and strategies other means of supporting the institutions to bridge-in existing gaps in terms of appointments, funding, staffing, and infrastructures.

Keywords: *Governing Council, Principal Officers, Infrastructure, Funding, Tertiary Institutions*

Introduction

Tertiary education as described by the Federal Republic of Nigeria in its National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013), is an education given after post basic education in institutions such as Universities and Inter-University Centres, Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, Monotechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI) and other institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs). Adeyemi in Opara (2023) stated that higher education is a system which embraces much of the country's research capacity and reproduces majority of the skilled professionals that are required in the labour market.

The governing councils of tertiary institutions in Nigeria are responsible for overseeing the management, administration, and governance of these institutions (Mgbekem, 2012). The council members are appointed to ensure effective leadership, accountability, and adherence to established policies and standards. The Governing Council of tertiary institution is the most important committee of the institution and is considered as the highest decision making body. The council holds very important roles in the development of the tertiary institution, in most cases the success or failure of any institution depends on how effective the committee members can perform their administrative functions (Mgbekem, 2012).

The functions of the Governing Councils as policy making organs in tertiary institutions include laying a general supervisory role over the administration of the institutions; serves as bridge between the government and the institution; protects the right of all in the College; ensure compliance to Government rules and policies; exercises general control over the finances of the institutions and ensure accountability; ensure judicious utilization of resources in accordance with government approved guidelines; responsible for the appointment of all senior staff through the appropriate Committees; approve budgets of the institutions, and ensure institutions solvency; be the custodian of all assets of the institutions; act as liaison between the institution and the visitor (Muhammadu, 2017).

The role of the governing council in the appointment of principal officers in Nigerian tertiary institutions is crucial in ensuring transparency, accountability, and the selection of qualified individuals for leadership positions. According to Ibrahim (2015), the governing council plays a vital role in approving the vacancy for the position of principal officers in a tertiary institution. When a vacancy arises, the council is responsible for initiating the process of selecting the new head of institutions or other principal officers. This is to ensure that the selection process is based on merit and the specific needs of the institution (Adekunle, 2019).

The governing council is also saddled with other responsibilities like the provision of infrastructural facilities within the tertiary institution. The Council's roles include planning, allocation of resources, and ensuring the availability of adequate infrastructure to support effective teaching, learning, and research (Ukase, 2011 and Adetunji, 2015). The council also review budget proposals and prioritize funding for infrastructure projects based on the institution's requirements and available resources. The governing council approves major infrastructure projects and ensures their effective implementation (Akinyemi & Abiddin, 2013).

Another essential role of the governing councils of Nigerian tertiary institutions is to ensure the provision of funds for these institutions. Kaul (2010) asserts that governing councils are responsible for overseeing financial matters, budget allocation, and resources management to ensure the sustainable functioning and development of the institutions. The governing council

collaborates with the management to prepare the annual budget for the institution. They review financial needs, assess priorities, and allocate funds to various segments and projects based on the college's objectives and strategic plans. The governing council exercises financial oversight by monitoring the financial performance of the college; they review financial statements, audit reports, and ensure compliance with financial regulations and reporting requirements for accountability (Okechukwu, 2011).

In the same vein the Governing Councils are required to regulate and facilitate staff recruitment, development and discipline in their respective tertiary institutions. As the highest decision making body, they are expected to set modalities, identify the basic needs and areas of priorities before any recruitment of staff. Councils are equally mandated to ensure that there is good staff development policies in place in the institution are strictly adhered to. Staff promotion and discipline are part and parcel of the duties bound on Governing Councils particularly that of senior staff in the College/Polytechnic without any fear or favour.

Statement of the Problem

Tertiary Institutions plays very vital role in ensuring the provision of quality post-secondary education in Nigeria; they shape the future of their graduands and impact the overall quality of education in society. Governing Councils being the overall decision making body in Tertiary Institutions; their importance in the overall administration of the institutions can never be over emphasized; they are saddled with the responsibilities of providing leadership, strategic direction, and accountability. Their actions and decisions impact the overall performance, growth, and development of the institutions, ultimately benefiting the students, staff, and the larger community.

However, it's observed that Tertiary Institutions in Jigawa State, Nigeria are faced with lots of administrative challenges; they are not been given full chance to recommend most suitable candidates in the position of head of institutions and other principal officers, they often struggle with inadequate funding which consequently hampers their ability to invest in adequacy the infrastructural development, instructional resources, and student support services, as well as daily expenses for running routine activities. Some of these institutions lack sufficient physical infrastructures, such as classrooms, libraries, and laboratories. Another challenge is for lack of consultations of the councils pertaining staff recruitment, development and discipline by the management of the institutions.

By implication these challenges may lead to the failure of those institutions in fulfilling their primary responsibilities of training students' at the higher level, and may also lead to failure in the accreditation of their academic programmes. The question is what's then the role of the school governing councils who are saddled with enormous responsibilities for ensuring effective management of the tertiary institutions, like the appointment of principal officers, provision of infrastructural facilities, funding the institutions, staff recruitment, development and discipline? It is on this basis that this research was intended to be carried out, that's to determine the influence of governing council in the administration of Tertiary Institutions in Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To ascertain the influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of principal officers of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the influence of Governing Councils on the funding of Tertiary Institutions of

Jigawa State, Nigeria.

3. To ascertain the influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
4. To ascertain the influence of Governing Councils on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of principal officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?
2. What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on funding Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?
3. What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?
4. What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Governing Councils have no significant influence on the appointment of principal officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
2. Governing Councils have no significant influence on funding Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
3. Governing Councils have no significant influence on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.
4. Governing Councils have no significant influence on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study hinged on survey research design; research questions were raised and answered; and four (4) hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study area was Tertiary Institutions in Jigawa state, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 1,386 senior academic and non-academic staff from the two (2) State owned Colleges of Education and two (2) State owned Polytechnics in Jigawa state, Nigeria. The sample size for this study was 302 drawn from using Research Advisors Table for determination of sample size at 95% confidence level. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire adapted from Doki, Idoko, and Kajo (2024) renamed as “Governing Council and Management of Tertiary Institutions Questionnaire” (GCAMTIQ); this instrument was

validated by experts in the field of research and management; and reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability estimation. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistic of Mean and Standard Deviation and inferential statistic of Chi-square.

Results:

Research Question 1

What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?

In answering this research question, mean and standard deviation of the responses of the respondents were computed.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Perceived Influence of Governing Councils on the Appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Make recommendation of candidates for appointment of principal officers.	384	2.75	0.79	Agree
2	Make investigation into any allegations made against the appointment of principal officers.	384	2.96	0.73	Agree
3	Take over the responsibility of appointing substantive principal officers.	384	2.84	0.76	Agree
4	Ensure that appointing the provost must be in line with the provisions of enabling laws.	384	2.62	0.66	Agree
5	Play major advisory roles in the appointment of the Principal Officers in tertiary institutions.	384	2.84	0.86	Agree
6	Draw up guidelines for the appointments of principal officers.	384	2.51	0.53	Agree
7	Conducting interview for the appointment of the principal officers.	384	3.06	0.88	Agree
8	Recommend the reappointment of the principal officers.	384	2.68	0.72	Agree
Grand Mean			2.78		Agree

Mean Score < than 2.50 = Disagree, Mean Score \geq 2.50 = Agree

The results presented in Table 1 revealed that all the 8 items on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria had their mean values ranged from 2.51 to 3.06, indicating that their mean values were above the mean cut-off point of 2.50. The grand mean of 2.78 shown in Table 1 indicates that Governing Councils have perceived positive influence on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Results on Table 1 further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.53 to 0.88, indicating that the responses of the respondents were not too far from the mean and from the opinion of one another on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on funding of tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Perceived Influence of Governing Councils on the Funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Facilitates research grants for conducting research on the Tertiary Institutions.	384	2.95	0.89	Agree
2	Enhance investment into new teaching facilities.	384	2.87	0.94	Agree
3	Lobby for financial support from private sectors.	384	2.64	0.61	Agree
4	Solicits financial support from spirited individuals.	384	2.73	0.64	Agree
5	Facilitate internally generated revenue (IGR) of the institutions.	384	3.09	0.98	Agree
6	Create avenue for funding.	384	3.05	0.90	Agree
7	Builds relationships to facilitate funding.	384	2.69	0.62	Agree
8	Ensure sustainability of relationships with Donor agencies.	384	2.95	0.83	Agree
Grand Mean			2.87		Agree

Mean Score < than 2.50 = Disagree, Mean Score \geq 2.50 = Agree

The results presented in Table 2 revealed that all the 8 items on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria had their mean values ranged from 2.64 to 3.09, indicating that their mean values were above the mean cut-off point of 2.50. The grand mean of 2.87 shown in Table 3 indicates that Governing Councils have perceived positive influence on the funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The Table further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.61 to 0.98, indicating that the responses of the respondents were not too far from the mean and from the opinion of one another on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Perceived Influence of Governing Councils on the Provision of Infrastructural Facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Ensure overall provision of infrastructural facilities.	384	2.94	0.69	Agree
2	Makes provision of mechanism for delivering short-term infrastructural goals.	384	2.57	0.73	Agree
3	Makes provision of mechanism for delivering mid-term infrastructural goals.	384	2.86	0.97	Agree
4	Ensure timely intervention to salvage the decay in infrastructural facilities in the Tertiary Institutions.	384	2.69	0.83	Agree
5	Approves the list of funds for purchases of furniture items.	384	3.14	0.85	Agree
6	Approves the list of funds for the purchase of office equipment.	384	2.89	0.77	Agree
7	Approves the list of funds for the installation of furniture items.	384	2.58	0.58	Agree
8	Ensure procession of assistance in terms of grants to enable delivery of key infrastructures to Tertiary Institutions.	384	2.76	0.81	Agree
Grand Mean			2.81		Agree

Mean Score < than 2.50 = Disagree, Mean Score ≥ 2.50 = Agree

The results presented in Table 3 revealed that all the 8 items on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria had their mean values ranged from 2.57 to 3.14, indicating that their mean values were above the mean cut-off point of 2.50. The grand mean of 2.87 shown in Table 2 indicates that Governing Councils have perceived positive influence on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Results on Table 2 further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.58 to 0.97, indicating that the responses of the respondents were not too far from the mean and from the opinion of one another on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question 4

What is the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Perceived Influence of Governing Councils on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Make modalities and requirements for staff recruitments in the institution	384	2.84	0.86	Agree
2	Ensure transparent processes for recruitment of all categories of staff	384	2.51	0.53	Agree
3	Approve only qualified candidates for employment into senior cadre offices	384	2.92	0.73	Agree
4	Ensure that staff promotions and advancement are merit-based	384	2.62	0.72	Agree
5	Staff development policy is in place and adhered to.	384	2.75	0.79	Agree
6	Ratification of study leave are made based on set standards	384	3.06	0.88	Agree
7	Ensure disciplinary procedures are established and enforced on any erring staff	384	2.84	0.76	Agree
8	Play role in addressing all sorts of misconduct and ensure equality to all staff.	384	2.51	0.66	Agree
Grand Mean			2.76		Agree

Mean Score < than 2.50 = Disagree, Mean Score ≥ 2.50 = Agree

The results presented in Table 4 revealed that all the 8 items on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the recruitment, development, and discipline of staff in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria had their mean values ranged from 2.51 to 3.06, indicating that their mean values were above the mean cut-off point of 2.50. The grand mean of 2.76 shown in Table 4 indicates that Governing Councils have perceived positive influence on the recruitment, development, and discipline of staff in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Results on Table 4 further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.53 to 0.88, indicating that the responses of the respondents were not too far from the mean and from the opinion of one another on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the recruitment, development, and discipline of staff in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis 1

Governing Councils have no significant influence on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Chi-square goodness of fit on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

	Observed N	Expected N	Df	Chi- square	Asymp. sig	Sig. value
SD	36	96.0	3	73.083	0.000	0.05
D	78	96.0				
A	130	96.0				
SA	140	96.0				
Total	384					

df= degree of freedom

The data presented on Table 5 shows that the Asymp. Sig value of 0.000 is less than the set significant value of 0.05 and this shows that the test of hypothesis is significant. This implies that Governing Councils have significant influence on the appointment of Principal Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Research Hypothesis 2

Governing Councils have no significant influence on funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Chi-square goodness of fit on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

	Observed N	Expected N	Df	Chi- square	Asymp. sig	Sig. value
SD	93	96.0	3	43.708	0.001	0.05
D	91	96.0				
A	99	96.0				
SA	101	96.0				
Total	384					

df= degree of freedom

The data presented on Table 6 shows that the Asymp. Sig value of 0.001 is less than the set significant value of 0.05 and this shows that the test of hypothesis is significant. This implies that Governing Councils have significant influence on funding of Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Research Hypothesis 3

Governing Councils have no significant influence on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Chi-square goodness of fit on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

	Observed N	Expected N	df	Chi- square	Asymp. sig	Sig. value
SD	91	96.0	3	53.792	0.000	0.05
D	43	96.0				
A	107	96.0				
SA	143	96.0				
Total	384					

df= degree of freedom

The data presented on Table 7 shows that the Asymp. Sig value of 0.000 is less than the set significant value of 0.05 and this shows that the test of hypothesis is significant. This implies that Governing Councils have significant influence on the provision of infrastructural facilities in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Research Hypothesis 4

Governing Councils have no significant influence on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Chi-square goodness of fit on the perceived influence of Governing Councils on the staff recruitment, development and discipline in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria

	Observed N	Expected N	Df	Chi- square	Asymp. sig	Sig. value
SD	63	96.0	3	48.708	0.001	0.05
D	91	96.0				
A	109	96.0				
SA	121	96.0				
Total	384					

df= degree of freedom

The data presented on Table 8 shows that the Asymp. Sig value of 0.001 is less than the set significant value of 0.05 and this shows that the test of hypothesis is significant. This implies that Governing Councils have significant influence on the recruitment, development and discipline of staff in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that Governing Councils have positive significant influence on the appointment of Principal Officers in Federal Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. The findings showed that governing councils make recommendation of candidates for appointment of Principal Officers; take over the responsibility of appointing substantive Principal Officers; play major advisory roles in the appointment of the Principal Officers; draw up guidelines for the appointment of Principal Officers; recommend the reappointment of the Principal Officers for another tenure. The finding of this study is in line with that of Doki, Idoko and Kajo (2024) that Governing Councils plays prominent roles in the appointment of Provosts of Federal Colleges of Education. In the same vein, Mulder (2017) who found out that in appointing a Provost, the Governing Council of the College is required by law to interview and recommend three candidates for the consideration of the Visitor and subsequent ratification by the President in Council.

The finding of the study also revealed that Governing Councils have positive significant influence on the funding of tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The findings showed that governing council facilitates research grants for conducting research on the tertiary institutions; enhance investment into new teaching facilities; lobby for financial support from private sectors; facilitate internally generated revenue (IGR) of the tertiary institutions with a view to support the institutions; builds relationships to facilitate funding. The finding of the study is in line with the view of Muhammadu (2017) who described the functions of Governing Councils of Colleges of Education to include: exercise general control over the finances of the institutions and ensure accountability. Similarly, Abdulkareem (2011) asserted that Governing Council lobby the relevant Educational Agencies or other bodies and statutory organizations in accordance with the law to seek for financial assistance or grants.

The finding of the study revealed that Governing Councils have positive significant influence on the provision of infrastructural facilities in tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The findings showed that governing council ensure overall provision of infrastructural facilities; makes provision of mechanism for delivering short term infrastructural goals; ensure timely intervention to salvage the decay in infrastructural facilities in the tertiary institutions; approves the list of funds for purchases of furniture items; approves the list of funds for the purchase of office equipment; ensure procession of assistance in terms of grants to enable delivery of key infrastructures to tertiary institutions. The findings corroborate with that of Doki, Idoko and Kajo (2024) that Governing Councils plays significant role in the provision of infrastructural facilities in Colleges of Education.

With regards to the finding of the study which revealed that Governing Councils have positive significant influence on the recruitment, development and discipline of staff in tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The findings showed that governing council of the tertiary institutions in Jigawa State ensure that transparent processes for recruitment of all categories of staff; staff promotions and advancement are merit-based; staff development policy is in place and adhered to; and that disciplinary procedures are established and enforced on any erring staff without sentiment. The findings of this study contradicts that of Ogunode and Sarkin-Fada (2023) who pointed out that poor capacity building programme and poor knowledge of tertiary institutions militates against poor performance of the Governing Councils in managing the affairs of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Governing Councils of the tertiary institutions in Jigawa State, Nigeria play very vital roles in the appointment of Principal Officers, provision of infrastructural facilities, funding, as well as staff recruitment, development and discipline in tertiary institutions of Jigawa State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Considering the roles played by Governing Councils in the management of tertiary institutions in Jigawa state; the government should ensure prompt appointment and or re-appointment of the members of the councils whenever their tenure lapses.
2. Governing Councils of tertiary institutions in Jigawa state, Nigeria should maintain the tempo in discharging their functions particularly on the appointment of substantive principal officers; funding; provision of infrastructures and staff recruitment, development and discipline.
3. The Governing Councils should equally continue working together with their College managers to upgrade the institutions and to bridge-in existing gaps in terms of appointments, funding, staffing, and infrastructures.

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